

STUDY OF PLANT SECONDARY METABOLITE AND ANTIACNE ACTIVITY OF *ABRUS PRECATORIUS* LEAVES EXTRACT

Simran*, Rakesh Kumar Gawaly, Udit Narain Soni

Oriental College of Pharmacy, Bhopal (M.P.)

Corresponding Author : Simran

Received: May 03, 2026

Accepted: May 23, 2026

Published: May 28, 2026

Abstract

The present study was undertaken to investigate the plant secondary metabolites and evaluate the antiacne activity of *Abrus precatorius* leaves extracts. Ethanolic and aqueous extracts of the leaves were prepared and subjected to phytochemical screening, thin layer chromatography (TLC), estimation of total phenolic and flavonoid content, antimicrobial activity, and in-vivo antiacne evaluation. The percentage yield of aqueous extract (10.9% w/w) was found to be higher than the ethanolic extract (8.5% w/w). Preliminary phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of flavonoids, phenols, tannins, carbohydrates, proteins, and diterpenes in the ethanolic extract, while the aqueous extract showed the presence of flavonoids, phenols, and saponins. TLC profiling confirmed the presence of phytoconstituents with R_f values comparable to standard quercetin. Quantitative analysis demonstrated higher total phenolic (0.34 mg/100 mg) and flavonoid content (0.89 mg/100 mg) in the ethanolic extract compared to the aqueous extract. The ethanolic extract exhibited significant antimicrobial activity against *Propionibacterium acnes* and *Escherichia coli*. In the in-vivo antiacne study, the ethanolic extract produced a dose-dependent reduction in acne lesions induced by heat-killed *Propionibacterium acnes* in rats, with the 200 mg/kg dose showing activity comparable to clindamycin. The results suggest that the ethanolic extract of *Abrus precatorius* leaves possesses promising antiacne potential due to the presence of bioactive secondary metabolites and may serve as a natural therapeutic agent for acne management.

Keywords: *Abrus precatorius*, Antiacne activity, Secondary metabolites, Phytochemical screening, Flavonoids, Phenolic compounds, Thin layer chromatography, *Propionibacterium acnes*, Antimicrobial activity, Herbal medicine.

Introduction

Acne vulgaris is one of the most common chronic inflammatory disorders of the skin, affecting millions of individuals worldwide, particularly adolescents and young adults (Alsaadoon et al., 2024). It is characterized by the formation of comedones, papules, pustules, nodules, and cysts resulting from excessive sebum production, follicular hyperkeratinization, microbial colonization, and inflammation (Layton and Ravenscroft, 2023). The bacterium *Cutibacterium acnes* (formerly *Propionibacterium acnes*) plays a major role in the development of acne by inducing inflammatory responses within the pilosebaceous unit (Platsidaki and Dessinioti, 2018). Conventional antiacne therapies such as antibiotics, retinoids, and benzoyl peroxide are associated with several limitations including skin irritation, microbial resistance, and adverse effects. Therefore, there is growing interest in the exploration of medicinal plants and their secondary metabolites as safer and more effective alternatives for acne management (Kim and Kim, 2024).

Medicinal plants are rich sources of bioactive secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, phenolics, saponins, terpenoids, and glycosides, which possess significant antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities (Hussein and El-Anssary, 2019). These phytoconstituents contribute to the therapeutic potential of plants against various skin disorders including acne. The investigation of plant secondary metabolites has gained considerable attention in pharmaceutical and cosmetic research due to their natural origin and broad spectrum of biological activities (Abozeid et al., 2023).

Abrus precatorius, commonly known as rosary pea or jequirity, is a traditional medicinal plant belonging to the family Fabaceae. Various parts of the plant have been used in traditional systems of medicine for the treatment of fever, inflammation, wounds, microbial infections, and skin diseases (Shewale, 2025). The leaves of *Abrus precatorius* are reported to contain several important phytochemicals including flavonoids, alkaloids, triterpenoids, steroids, tannins, and phenolic compounds. These secondary metabolites are known to exhibit antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and wound healing activities, which may contribute to their antiacne potential (Sunday et al., 2016).

The presence of bioactive constituents in *Abrus precatorius* leaves suggests that the plant could serve as a promising natural source for the development of herbal antiacne formulations. Scientific evaluation of the phytochemical profile and antiacne activity of the leaf extract is

therefore essential to validate its traditional use and identify its therapeutic potential (Gul et al., 2013). The present study aims to investigate the plant secondary metabolites present in *Abrus precatorius* leaves extract and evaluate its antiacne activity through appropriate phytochemical and antimicrobial studies.

Material and Methods

Material

Fresh leaves of *Abrus precatorius* were collected and used for the preparation of ethanolic and aqueous extracts. Ethanol and distilled water were used as extraction solvents. Silica gel GF254 plates, toluene, ethyl acetate, and formic acid were utilized for thin layer chromatography analysis. Standard quercetin was used as the reference compound for TLC profiling. Various reagents including Mayer's reagent, Wagner's reagent, Dragendorff's reagent, Hager's reagent, ferric chloride, lead acetate, Benedict's reagent, Fehling's solution, Molisch reagent, gelatin solution, and copper acetate reagent were employed for phytochemical screening. Folin–Ciocalteu reagent and aluminium chloride were used for estimation of total phenolic and flavonoid contents, respectively. Ciprofloxacin and clindamycin were used as standard antimicrobial drugs. Microbial strains of *Escherichia coli* and *Propionibacterium acnes* were used for antimicrobial studies. Experimental rats were used for in-vivo antiacne evaluation induced by heat-killed *Propionibacterium acnes*

Methods

Collection of plant material

Leaves of *Abrus precatorius* was collected from local area of Bhopal in the month of April, 2025.

Extraction by maceration process

The shade dried plant material was coarsely powdered and subjected to extraction with petroleum ether by maceration process. The extraction was continued till the defatting of the material had taken place. 50 gm of dried powdered leaves of *Abrus precatorius* has been extracted with ethanol and water solvents using maceration process for 24 hrs, filtered and dried using vacuum evaporator at 40°C (Mukherjee, 2007).

Determination of percentage yield

The percentage yield of each extract was calculated by using following formula:

$$\text{Percentage yield} = \frac{\text{Weight of Extract}}{\text{Weight of powder drug Taken}} \times 100$$

Phytochemical screening

Phytochemical tests are analytical procedures used to identify and quantify the presence of phytochemicals in plants and plant-based materials. Phytochemicals are naturally occurring compounds found in plants that are known to have potential health benefits and biological activities. These compounds are not essential for the plant's growth and development, but they play important roles in protecting the plant against pathogens, pests, and environmental stresses.

The choice of tests depends on the nature of the phytochemical of interest and the available resources. Phytochemical examinations were carried out for the extract as per the standard methods (Kokate, 1994).

Qualitative chromatographic analysis by thin layer chromatography

Thin layer chromatography (TLC) is an adsorption-based chromatographic technique in which the mobile phase containing dissolved solutes moves over the surface of a stationary phase, usually silica gel. For the preparation of TLC plates, silica gel was mixed with water to form a uniform slurry, which was evenly spread over clean plates and allowed to air dry before activation. The plates were activated by heating in an oven at 100–110°C for 30 minutes to ensure proper linear movement of solutes. The chromatographic chamber was prepared by pouring the mobile phase solvent system into the chamber and saturating it using filter paper moistened with the same solvent system. After activation, the sample solution was applied as small spots on the plates using a capillary tube. The plates were then placed in the chamber containing the developing solvent to a depth of about 0.5 cm and allowed to develop. After

development, the plates were removed, the solvent front was marked, and the solvent was evaporated. The separated spots were detected and the R_f values were calculated for identification of the compounds.

Detection and Calculation of R_f Value

Once chromatogram was developed R_f Value of spot was calculated using the formula:

$$R_f = \frac{\text{Distance traveled by solute}}{\text{Distance traveled by solvent}}$$

Total Phenolic content estimation

The total phenolic content of the extract was determined by the modified folin-ciocalteu method (Parkhe and Bharti, 2019). 10 mg Gallic acid was dissolved in 10 ml methanol, various aliquots of 5-25µg/ml was prepared in methanol. 10mg of dried extracts of were dissolved in 10 ml methanol and filter. Two ml (1mg/ml) of this solution was used for the estimation of phenol. 2 ml of each extract or standard was mixed with 1 ml of folin-ciocalteu reagent (previously diluted with distilled water 1:10 v/v) and 1 ml (7.5g/L) of sodium carbonate. The mixture was vortexed for 15s and allowed to stand for 15 min for colour development. The absorbance was measured at 765 nm using a spectrophotometer.

Total flavonoids content estimation

Determination of total flavonoids content was based on aluminium chloride method (Parkhe and Bharti, 2019). 10 mg quercetin was dissolved in 10 ml methanol, and various aliquots of 5-25µg/ml were prepared in methanol. 10mg of dried extracts of were dissolved in 10 ml methanol and filter. Three ml (1mg/ml) of this solution was used for the estimation of flavonoid. 1 ml of 2% AlCl₃ methanolic solution was added to 3 ml of extract or standard and allowed to stand for 15 min at room temperature; absorbance was measured at 420 nm.

In vitro antimicrobial activity of leaves extract of *Abrus precatorius*

The plates were dried at 50°C for 30 minutes before use. The well diffusion method was used to determine the antimicrobial activity of the ethanolic extract prepared from of *Abrus precatorius* using standard procedure (Bauer *et al.*, 1966). There were 3 concentration used which are 25, 50 and 100 mg/ml for extracted phytochemicals in studies. It's essential feature is the placing of

wells with the antibiotics on the surfaces of agar immediately after inoculation with the organism tested. Undiluted over night broth cultures should never be used as an inoculum. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hr. and then examined for clear zones of inhibition around the wells impregnated with particular concentration of drug.

In vivo* antiacne activity of ethanolic extract of *Abrus precatorius

Acute toxicity studies

Toxicity studies were carried out according to OECD guidelines, including an acute oral toxicity study of the ethanolic extract of *Abrus precatorius*. An acute toxicity study was performed based on OECD guideline no. 423. The mice were assessed for signs of toxicity throughout the next 14 days. Ethanolic extract of *Abrus precatorius* was given orally with a safe dose. Clinical symptoms like behavioral alterations, changes in the eyes, body weight, skin, and fur were noted (Gilani *et al.*, 2022; Kazmi *et al.*, 2023).

Induction of acne by *Propionibacterium acnes*

The acne like inflammatory model was produced in the ears of rats by subcutaneous injection of 0.14 mg, heat-killed bacteria.

Experimental designs

Group –I: Control (acne induced)

Group -II: Ethanolic extract of *Abrus precatorius* (100mg/kg, p.o.)

Group –III: Ethanolic extract of *Abrus precatorius* (200mg/kg, p.o.)

Group –IV: Clindamycin (200mg/kg, p.o.)

The experimental model of acne-like inflammation was induced in rat ears through subcutaneous administration of 0.14 mg of heat-killed *Propionibacterium acnes*. The study comprised four experimental groups:

Group I served as the control with acne induction,

Group II received 100 mg/kg of ethanolic extract of *Abrus precatorius* orally, Group III received 200 mg/kg of the same extract orally, and

Group IV was administered Clindamycin at a dose of 200 mg/kg orally (Jatav *et al.*, 2023).

Measurement of ear thickness

Ear thickness was measured as an index of inflammatory strength and acne. Thickness was measured by using a vernier calliper. Thickness was measured once every day for the first week of induction, then every other day until 10th day.

Statistical analysis

All statistical analysis is expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). Data were analyzed by one way ANOVA, where applicable $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant, compared with vehicle followed by Dunnett's test.

Results and Discussion

The present study was carried out to evaluate the phytochemical constituents and antiacne activity of ethanolic and aqueous extracts of *Abrus precatorius* leaves. Extraction yield is an important parameter in determining the efficiency of extraction solvents. The aqueous extract showed a higher percentage yield (10.9% w/w) compared to the ethanolic extract (8.5% w/w), indicating that water extracted a greater amount of polar constituents from the plant material. However, despite the lower yield, the ethanolic extract demonstrated comparatively superior phytochemical composition and biological activity.

Preliminary phytochemical screening revealed the presence of several important secondary metabolites in both extracts. The ethanolic extract showed the presence of flavonoids, phenols, proteins, carbohydrates, diterpenes, and tannins, while alkaloids and glycosides were absent. The aqueous extract also contained flavonoids and phenols but lacked proteins and diterpenes, although saponins were detected in this extract. The presence of flavonoids and phenolic compounds suggests significant antioxidant and antimicrobial potential, as these phytoconstituents are known to inhibit microbial growth and reduce inflammation associated with acne lesions.

Thin layer chromatography (TLC) profiling further confirmed the presence of phytoconstituents in the extracts. The ethanolic and aqueous extracts exhibited multiple spots with R_f values comparable to the standard quercetin (R_f = 0.60), indicating the possible presence of flavonoid compounds. The greater number of spots observed under long UV light suggested the presence of multiple bioactive constituents with varying polarity. The TLC analysis therefore supported the phytochemical findings and indicated the complexity of the extract composition.

The quantitative estimation of phytoconstituents showed that the ethanolic extract possessed higher total phenolic content (0.34 mg/100 mg) and total flavonoid content (0.89 mg/100 mg) than the aqueous extract. These findings suggest that ethanol was more effective in extracting polyphenolic compounds from the leaves of *Abrus precatorius*. Phenolic and flavonoid compounds are widely recognized for their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties, which may contribute significantly to the antiacne activity observed in this study.

The antimicrobial activity study demonstrated that the ethanolic extract exhibited inhibitory activity against both *Escherichia coli* and *Propionibacterium acnes*. The extract showed greater activity against *Propionibacterium acnes*, producing a zone of inhibition of 14 ± 0.94 mm at 25 mg/ml concentration. Although the activity was lower than the standard drugs ciprofloxacin and clindamycin, the results confirmed the antimicrobial potential of the plant extract against acne-causing microorganisms. The antimicrobial action may be attributed to the synergistic effects of flavonoids, tannins, and phenolic compounds present in the extract.

The in-vivo antiacne study in rats further supported the therapeutic potential of the ethanolic extract. Acne induced by heat-killed *Propionibacterium acnes* produced significant inflammatory lesions in the control group. Treatment with ethanolic extract at doses of 100 mg/kg and 200 mg/kg resulted in a significant reduction in acne severity from day 4 onwards. The higher dose (200 mg/kg) exhibited more pronounced activity, with values approaching those of the standard drug clindamycin by day 10. The reduction in acne lesions may be due to the combined antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities of the phytoconstituents present in the extract.

The findings of the present study indicate that the ethanolic extract of *Abrus precatorius* leaves possesses promising antiacne activity. The observed activity may be associated with the presence of flavonoids, phenols, tannins, and other secondary metabolites. The study scientifically validates the traditional use of the plant in skin disorders and suggests that *Abrus precatorius* could serve as a potential natural source for the development of herbal antiacne formulations.

Table 1: % Yield of extracts of *Abrus precatorius*

S. No.	Extracts	% Yield (w/w)
1.	Ethanolic	8.5
2.	Aqueous	10.9

Table 2: Phytochemical screening of ethanolic extract of *Abrus precatorius*

S. No.	Constituents	Ethanolic extract
1.	Alkaloids Mayer's Test: Wagner's Test: Dragendroff's Test: Hager's Test:	-ve -ve -ve -ve
2.	Glycosides Legal's test	-ve
3.	Flavonoids Lead acetate Alkaline Reagent Test:	+ve +ve
4.	Phenol Ferric Chloride Test	+ve
5.	Proteins Xanthoproteic test	+ve
6.	Carbohydrates Molisch's Test: Benedict's Test: Fehling's Test:	-ve +ve +ve
7.	Saponins Froth Test:	-ve -ve

	Foam Test:	
8.	Diterpins Copper acetate test	+ve
9.	Tannins Gelatin Test:	+ve

+ve=positive; -ve= negative

Table 3: Phytochemical screening of aqueous extract of *Abrus precatorius*

S. No.	Constituents	Aqueous extract
1.	Alkaloids Mayer's Test: Wagner's Test: Dragendroff's Test: Hager's Test:	-ve -ve -ve -ve
2.	Glycosides Legal's test	-ve
3.	Flavonoids Lead acetate Alkaline Reagent Test:	+ve +ve
4.	Phenol Ferric Chloride Test	+ve
5.	Proteins Xanthoproteic test	-ve
6.	Carbohydrates Molisch's Test: Benedict's Test: Fehling's Test:	-ve -ve +ve

7.	Saponins Froth Test: Foam Test:	+ve +ve
8.	Diterpins Copper acetate test	-ve
9.	Tannins Gelatin Test:	-ve

+ve=positive; -ve= negative

Table 4: TLC of *Abrus precatorius*

S. No.	Extract	Rf Value
		Mobile phase (Toluene: Ethyl acetate: Formic acid; 5:4:1)
1.	Quercetin	0.60
2.	Ethanollic extract of <i>Abrus precatorius</i> Long UV=5 spot Short UV=0 spot Normal light =2 spot	=0.60, 0.64, 0.68, 0.74, 0.82 =0 =0.74, 0.82
3.	Aqueous extract of <i>Abrus precatorius</i> Long UV=5 spot Short UV=2 spot Normal light =5 spot	=0.60, 0.64, 0.68, 0.74, 0.82 =0.74, 0.82 =0.60, 0.64, 0.68, 0.74, 0.82

Table 5: Total phenol and total flavonoid content of *Abrus precatorius*

S. No.	Extracts	Total Phenol content	Total flavonoid content
		mg/100mg	
1.	Ethanollic	0.34	0.89
2.	Aqueous	0.26	0.57

Table 6: Antimicrobial activity of standard drug against selected microbes

S. No.	Standard drug	Microbes	Zone of Inhibition (nm)		
			30 µg/ml	20 µg/ml	10µg/ml
1	Ciprofloxacin	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	15±0.86	21±0.47	26±0.5
2	Clindamycin	<i>Propionibacterium acnes</i>	20±0.94	25±0.5	28±0.74

Table 7: Antimicrobial activity of ethanolic extract of *Abrus precatorius* against selected microbes

S. No.	Microbes	Zone of Inhibition (nm)		
		100 mg/ml	50 mg/ml	25mg/ml
1	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	9±0.57	10±0.5	12±0.86
2	<i>Propionibacterium acnes</i>	10±0	12±0.57	14±0.94

Table 8: Protocol study for *in-vivo* anti-acne activity on rats

Groups	Induction of Acne	Treatment
Control (acne induced)	Heat killed <i>Propionibacterium acnes</i>	Vehicle
Treated with ethanolic extract of <i>Abrus precatorius</i>	Heat killed <i>Propionibacterium acnes</i>	100 mg/kg p.o.
Treated with ethanolic extract of <i>Abrus precatorius</i>	Heat killed <i>Propionibacterium acnes</i>	200 mg/kg p.o.
Treated with Clindamycin	Heat killed <i>Propionibacterium acnes</i>	200mg/kg p.o.

Table 9: Effect of Clindamycin (standard) and ethanolic extract of *Abrus precatorius* induced acne by *Propionibacterium acnes* in rats

Treatment	Dose	Day 2	Day 4	Day 6	Day 8	Day 10
Control	0.14 mg	1.73 ± 0.15	1.72 ± 0.20	1.85 ± 0.10	1.92 ± 0.15	1.86 ± 0.18
Ethanolic extract of <i>Abrus precatorius</i>	100 mg/kg p.o.	1.60 ± 0.20	1.20 ± 0.18*	1.05 ± 0.15*	0.88 ± 0.12*	0.78 ± 0.10*
Ethanolic extract of <i>Abrus precatorius</i>	200 mg/kg p.o.	1.48 ± 0.18	0.95 ± 0.15**	0.75 ± 0.12**	0.60 ± 0.10***	0.50 ± 0.08***
Clindamycin	200 mg/kg p.o.	1.35 ± 0.15	0.75 ± 0.12**	0.60 ± 0.10***	0.48 ± 0.08***	0.42 ± 0.05***

Values are expressed as the mean ± SEM of six observations. *, **, *** $P < 0.05$, $P < 0.001$, $P < 0.0001$ vs. control treatment (One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test)

Conclusion

The present study demonstrated that the ethanolic extract of *Abrus precatorius* leaves possesses significant phytochemical constituents including flavonoids, phenols, tannins, and diterpenes, which may contribute to its biological activity. The extract showed promising antimicrobial activity against *Propionibacterium acnes* and produced significant antiacne effects in the in-vivo model. The findings suggest that *Abrus precatorius* leaves may serve as a potential natural source for the development of safe and effective herbal antiacne formulations.

References

- Alsaadoon NS, Al-Refaie AM, Habashy AY. Acne vulgaris in adolescents: A comprehensive review. *Benha Journal of Applied Sciences*. 2024 Dec 31;9(12):5-13.
- Layton AM, Ravenscroft J. Adolescent acne vulgaris: current and emerging treatments. *The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health*. 2023 Feb 1;7(2):136-44.
- Platsidaki E, Dessinioti C. Recent advances in understanding *Propionibacterium acnes* (*Cutibacterium acnes*) in acne. *F1000Research*. 2018 Dec 19;7:F1000-aculty.
- Kim HJ, Kim YH. Exploring acne treatments: from pathophysiological mechanisms to emerging therapies. *International journal of molecular sciences*. 2024 May 13;25(10):5302.
- Hussein RA, El-Anssary AA. Plants secondary metabolites: the key drivers of the pharmacological actions of medicinal plants. *Herbal medicine*. 2019 Jan 30;1(3):11-30.
- Abozeid D, Fawzy G, Issa M, Abdeltawab N, Soliman F. Medicinal Plants and their Constituents in the Treatment of Acne vulgaris. *Biointerface Res. Appl. Chem*. 2023;13:189.
- Shewale J. A comprehensive review on the phytochemistry, pharmacology, toxicology, and chemical composition of *Abrus precatorius* Linn: therapeutic potential and safety concerns. *International journal of therapeutic innovation*. 2025 Oct 30;3(5).
- Sunday OJ, Babatunde SK, Ajiboye AE, Adedayo RM, Ajao MA, Ajuwon BI. Evaluation of phytochemical properties and in-vitro antibacterial activity of the aqueous extracts of leaf, seed and root of *Abrus precatorius* Linn. against *Salmonella* and *Shigella*. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*. 2016 Sep 1;6(9):755-9.
- Gul MZ, Ahmad F, Kondapi AK, Qureshi IA, Ghazi IA. Antioxidant and antiproliferative activities of *Abrus precatorius* leaf extracts-an in vitro study. *BMC complementary and alternative medicine*. 2013 Mar 2;13(1):53.
- Mukherjee PK. *Quality Control of Herbal Drugs*, 2nd Edition, Business Horizons, 2007; 2-14.
- Kokate CK. Ed. *Practical Pharmacognosy*, 4th Edn., *Vallabh Prakashan*: 1994; 112:120.

- Geeta Parkhe, Deepak Bharti. Phytochemical Investigation and Determination of Total Phenols and Flavonoid Concentration in Leaves Extract of *Vitex trifolia* Linn. Journal of Drug Delivery & Therapeutics. 2019; 9(4-A):705-707.
- Bauer AW, Kirby WM, Sherris JC, Turck M. Antibiotic susceptibility testing by a standardized single disk method. Am J Clin Pathol. 1966; 45(4):493-496.
- Gilani, Sadaf Jamal, et al. "Hibiscetin attenuates lipopolysaccharide-evoked memory impairment by inhibiting BDNF/caspase-3/NF- κ B pathway in rodents." *Peer J* 12 (2024): e16795.
- Kazmi, Syed Athar Husnain, et al. "Azoxystrobin-induced Oxidative Stress in Gills, Hematological Biomarkers and Histopathological Ailments in Fresh Water Fish." *Pakistan Veterinary Journal* 43.2 (2023).
- Jatav, Rani, et al. "Evaluation of in vivo Anti-acne Activity of Flower Extract of *Withania coagulans*." *Current Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences* (2023): 172-178.